

PART 1 USE CASE

Sea level comparison North Sea/Mediterranean

058.005 Introduction into Research Data Management

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Abstract:

This experiment aimed to explore the potential relationship between sea levels in the North Sea and the Mediterranean Sea over the past 20 years. Data for this analysis was obtained from the National Oceanography Centre – Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, focusing on two key locations: Venice, Italy, representing the Mediterranean Sea, and Vlissingen, Netherlands, representing the North Sea. The primary research question driving this investigation was whether a discernible relationship exists between the sea levels of these two distinct bodies of water.

1. Use case

Methodology:

The experiment involved the collection and analysis of sea level data spanning two decades from both Venice (*Data and station information for VENEZIA II, 2022*) and Vlissingen (*Data and station information for VLISSINGEN, 2022*). The data from the National Oceanography Centre – Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level served as the foundation for this analysis (Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL), 2023). The objective was to investigate potential patterns between sea levels in the Mediterranean Sea and the North Sea.

Input Data:

The primary input for this experiment was the sea level data obtained from the designated locations over the past 20 years. These two datasets included average annual measurements.

Data Processing:

The sea level data from Venice and Vlissingen was imported into Python and processed. The data was shortened to 20 years and put into a line diagram. The least squares method was used to create a better understanding of a possible trend.

Output:

The main output of this experiment was an analysis of the relationship between sea levels in the North Sea and the Mediterranean Sea. The processed data was visualized through a line diagram, providing a graphical representation of the trends observed over the 20-year period. Additionally, the least squares method, a statistical approach for linear regression, was applied to identify and quantify any linear relationships between the sea levels of the two seas.

Results and Conclusions

According to the least squares method applied to the dataset, it was observed that the sea levels in both the Mediterranean Sea (represented by Venice, Italy) and the North Sea (represented by Vlissingen, Netherlands) exhibited a consistent upward trend over the two-decade period.

In the Mediterranean Sea, the sea level demonstrated a more pronounced increase, with a rise of approximately 138.5 mm over the 20-year period. This corresponds to an average annual increase of approximately 6.9 mm per year. The higher tempo of sea level rise in the Mediterranean Sea raises concerns about potential impacts on coastal areas and ecosystems in the region.

Conversely, in the North Sea, the sea level showed a somewhat lower rate of increase, with a rise of approximately 46.4 mm over the same 20-year period. This corresponds to an average annual increase of approximately 2.3 mm per year.

Figure 1, Result in Python by Pelle Limburg, 2023

References

Data and station information for VENEZIA II. (2022).

<https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/2100.php>

Data and station information for VLISSINGEN. (2022).

<https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/20.php>

Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL). (2023). <https://psmsl.org/>

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Data management plan (DMP)

Relationship Between Sea Levels in the North Sea and the Mediterranean Sea: A 20-Year Analysis

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	dd/mm/yyyy	First version of DMP – created for start of project (deliverable xy)
2.0	dd/mm/yyyy	Second version of DMP – prepared for midterm review (deliverable xz)

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) .
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Project details

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Funder, funding programme, grant number	
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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	sealevel_experiment_Vlissingen_Venice.csv	Plain text		100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Annual data venitia II	https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/rlr.annual.data/2100.rlrdata		no
R2	Annual data Vlissingen	https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/rlr.annual.data/20.rlrdata		no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data is downloaded as CSV files and processed in Python.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in Data Management Plan Sea level comparison North Sea/Mediterranean and include a timestamp of creation. Version control is automated.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The CSV files or accessible online and the python code is uploaded.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: calibration.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2023-12-13			CC BY 4.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The use of Python/Jupyter notebooks is required.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1		10 years	Students and general public

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The [PI / data officer XY] will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value

Estimated total costs		0
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Additional description (if required):